

Step 3. Semi-structured Interviews

Topic 1: Experiences

- How would you describe the experience of the task?
 - What was important to you while selecting a playlist?
- What are your thoughts on the added explanations?
 - Did the explanations change what was important to you while selecting a playlist?
 - (in general) How much did you care about the descriptions accompanying the playlists?
 - For each category, do you think you would have selected playlists differently if you'd already had the descriptions from the start?
 - Genre
 - Popularity
 - Gender
 - Country
 - (in general) Would you like having such descriptions available for playlists offered on streaming platforms?

Topic 2: Perception and understanding of unfairness in MRS (streaming services)

- Before you did the experiment, did you ever consider music streaming services to be fair, or unfair, to artists?
 - If yes, what did you think was unfair in the systems?
 - If no, what do you think an algorithm that is fair to *artists* could entail?
- To what extent do you think the algorithms in streaming platforms are fair to artists?
 - What do you think may cause unfairness there?
- Has the experiment changed your current perception and understanding of causes of unfairness in music streaming services?
 - If yes, how would you describe this change?
 - If no, could you describe why?

Topic 3: User representation & experience of fairness

- How would you describe a music streaming service that is fair to (end) users?
- Did you feel like in the playlists in this task, the system understood your music taste?
 - How about in the music streaming services you normally use?
- Do you feel well-represented in that system? In what way?
 - (if not yet covered) Do you find that the platform recognizes your music taste?
 - (if not yet covered) Do you feel like the community that you associate yourself with is represented?
- Do music streaming services help you in exploring new music?
 - Do you use them often?
- Do you personally feel treated fairly by the music streaming services?
 - Why (not)?